

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

1/11/2022 – 31/10/2025

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T1.3_Greek Lab 3rd Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Technical Chamber of Greece – Department of Eastern Crete, Conference Hall, Prevelaki and Grevenon, 712 02, Heraklion, Greece.

EVENT DATE: Wednesday, 29 May 2024 (Duration: 2 hours)

EVENT TITLE: Co-creation Workshop on Offshore Wind Farms in Greece: Building Bridges Facing Challenges

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: EMD – European Maritime Day 2024

- Συνάντηση Εργασίας
- Τετάρτη 29 Μαΐου 2024
18:00 – 20:00
- Τεχνικό Επιμελητήριο Ελλάδας
Τμήμα Ανατολικής Κρήτης

Υπεράκτια Αιολικά Πάρκα στην Ελλάδα:
Δημιουργώντας Γέφυρες,
Αντιμετωπίζοντας τις Προκλήσεις

LEAD ORGANISER: Q-PLAN International

CO-ORGANISER: Minoan Energy Community

LANGUAGE: Greek

CONCEPT: The MARINEWIND 3rd co-creation workshop aimed to bring together different Greek stakeholders interested in the developments of Offshore wind in Greece, in order to discuss and explore the challenges and opportunities of the Floating Offshore Wind Technologies (FOWTs) in Greece. The workshop was organised at the Technical Chamber of Greece in Heraklion, Crete. The targeted location was a great opportunity to gather interested in FOWTs audience from all the different key stakeholders, particularly civil society, academics and industrial stakeholders, to discuss the techno-economic aspect of FOWTs as well as the local communities' concerns in terms of developing FOWT projects in Crete, thus resulting in a more sustainable development of the offshore wind sector in the respective area. Crete is among the first areas where Floating Offshore Wind farms will be developed, thus resulting in increased interest from the local community about the event.

The workshop aimed to inform the participants about the MARINEWIND project and explore the Greek and European spatial planning in terms of FOWTs along with their technical challenges and economic elements. Additionally, the workshop pursued to identify the level of social acceptance regarding the investment on FOWTs in Greece and in particular around the area of Crete through a co-creation session, where participants were actively participated, sharing their knowledge and expertise, and expressed their views on what is needed in order to accelerate the commercialisation and deployment of FOWTs in Greece.

OBJECTIVES

- Increase awareness on FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Identify critical barriers and enablers on FOWTs in order to accelerate the investment and commercialization these technologies.
- Increase Social acceptance on FOWTs facilities and installations by directly involving local communities and citizens and by addressing potential environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in Greek MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE:

Considering that Crete is one of the selected areas for the development of the first FOWTs in Greece, the 3rd co-creation workshop targeted mainly representatives from civil society to explore their perceptions and concerns, but also having the strong presence of industrial stakeholders as well as public authorities, academics and green innovators, directly or indirectly involved in the Greek Lab. For each specific category, the involved actors were:

- **Industry:** FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, tech/project developers, trade associations (fisheries and tourism).
- **Academia:** Scientific & Research Community.
- **Public authorities:** National Regulatory authority for energy, policymakers.
- **Civil society:** NGOs, civil society organisations, and citizens.
- **Green innovation:** SMEs, environmental organisations.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 34 participants

Figure 1: Participants overview

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

The 3rd MARINEWIND co-creation workshop kicked-off with a brief presentation of the project objectives, activities and preliminary results, by the Project Manager of Q-PLAN International, Leonidas Parodos. The project overview was followed by five speeches, covering various aspects of the Offshore Wind Energy and Technologies in Greece, focusing on FOWTs, as depicted in the following sub-sections. The co-creation workshop concluded with the respective co-creation session and a dedicated roundtable among participants, discussing challenges and barriers in terms of developing FOWTs in Crete.

2.1 Maritime Spatial Planning and Offshore Wind Farms in Greece and Europe

The opening speech started with a comprehensive overview of a generic framework for Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP), the actions of EU and member states towards MSP and sustainable blue economy, the benefits associated with the development of Offshore Wind Farms along with best practices, by the Vice Governor of Crete on European and International Affairs, Alexakis Georgios.

Mr. Alexakis presented the concept of MSP as a fundamental tool, highlighting its role towards Sustainable Blue Economy. Furthermore, he outlined the correlation between MSP and European Green Deal as well as the key role in increasing the offshore wind capacity in Europe respecting the protected areas and restoring several EU's Sea areas.

Following that, Mr. Alexakis referred to the binding European Directive on MSP ([Directive 2014/89/EU](#)) along with the obligations of the member states, and the barriers delaying Greece from developing a national or regional MSP.

Finally, he outlined the potential and benefits of the Offshore Wind Farms as well as the needs leading to the transition to Renewable Energy Sources:

- Climate Crisis
- Decarbonization
- Independence from fossil fuels
- Reduction of CO2 emissions
- Saturation on land areas
- Undervalued potential at sea areas

Figure 2: Mean annual wind energy potential in the Mediterranean

2.2 Floating Wind Turbine technologies

The next speech focused on existing technologies of Offshore Wind Farms as well as installed and planned projects around the world, by Professor of the Hellenic Mediterranean University and Founding Member of the Minoan Energy Community, Katsaprakakis Dimitrios.

Mr. Katsaprakakis introduced several interesting statistics regarding several operative Offshore Wind Farm projects around Europe, outlining also the platform types implemented in the Bottom Fixed and Floating Offshore Wind Farms.

Figure 3: Types of Bottom Fixed Offshore Wind Turbines

Regarding the Floating Offshore Wind Farms, two types of platforms have been implemented so far:

- 1) Equinor's Hywind Spar (Hywind Scotland, 30 MW, 2017)
- 2) Principle Power's WindFloat (WindFloat Atlantic, 25 MW, 2019 | Kincardine, 50 MW, 2012)

Figure 4: Hywind Spar platform

Beyond the above platform types, there are 20 more platform designs that have reached the testing phase in realistic sea conditions and another 80 that are in earlier stages of development.

Mr. Katsaprakakis then presented the basic principles of movement of a Floating Wind Turbine, as depicted in the figure below, and its stabilization methods, particularly the (i) **gravity-stabilization**, (ii) **waterplane-stabilization**, and (iii) **mooring-stabilization**.

Figure 5: Movements of Floating Wind Turbines

The speech closed with reference to existing Floating Offshore Wind Farms, including pilots, along with planned projects for the following years that are going to implement the WindFloat platform type.

Figure 6: WindFloat platform

2.3 Offshore Wind Turbine Maintenance technologies

Following the existing technologies of Offshore Wind Turbines, Kontaxakis Kostas, Professor of the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Hellenic Mediterranean University, introduced the possible failures of Offshore Wind Turbines along with the maintenance technologies to prevent them.

Specifically, Mr. Kontaxakis referred to the importance of maintenance on the Offshore Wind Turbines, outlining the most critical parts of the turbine that may fail during their operation and the challenges to prevent or mitigate their failure. Specifically, five component groups are responsible for a total of 67% of failures:

- Electrical System
- Plant Control System
- Sensors
- Hydraulic System
- Yaw System

Figure 7: Subassemblies in terms of failure rate

Additionally, Mr. Kontaxakis highlighted the general objectives of maintenance protocols, which are:

- Increase of **Reliability** (R)
- Reduction of **Maintainability** (M)
- Increase of **Availability** $[R/(R+M)]$

Finally, towards achieving the above goals, Mr. Kontaxakis presented three basic Maintenance methods:

- **Corrective** maintenance that is triggered after a breakdown,
- **Preventive** maintenance based on time planning, and
- **Predictive** maintenance based on measurements of the actual condition of the equipment.

Figure 8: Wind Turbine blade failure

2.4 Economic elements of Offshore Wind Farms

The next speech focused on the economic elements of Floating and Bottom fixed Offshore Wind Farms and their comparison, by Papadakis Nikolaos, Professor at the Hellenic Mediterranean University.

Specifically, Mr. Papadakis presented three important economic elements:

- Levelised Cost of Energy – **LCOE**
- Capital Expenditures – **CAPEX**
- Operational Expenditures – **OPEX**

The function connecting the above elements is:
$$LCOE = \frac{CAPEX + \sum_i^T \frac{OPEX_i}{(1+r)^i}}{\sum_i^T \frac{AEP_i}{(1+r)^i}}$$

where (i) “**AEP**” is the Annual Energy Production, (ii) “**T**” is the project’s lifetime in years, and (iii) “**r**” is the cost of money/interest rate.

Mr. Papadakis analysed the CAPEX and OPEX for the Floating and Bottom fixed Offshore Wind Farms during his speech and compared the respective LCOE. Based on the existing literature and results, he drew some conclusions for the LCOE regarding the Floating Offshore Wind Farms:

- LCOE is strongly dependent on the distance from the shore and the wind capacity.
- So far, the LCOE is more than 0.10 €/KWh, but the downtrends are faster than expected.

Figure 9: North Atlantic LCOE map for Floating Offshore Wind Farms

2.5 Offshore Wind Farms – Challenges and Prospects

The final speech focused on the challenges and prospects of Offshore Wind Farms, by Aristides Kyprakis, Professor at the University of Edinburgh.

During his speech, he highlighted the need to reduce CO₂ emissions and the role of Offshore Wind Farms towards the Green Energy transition. Furthermore, he presented the existing interconnection technologies along with their benefits and barriers.

Finally, Mr. Kyprakis underlined that although there are major challenges for Offshore Wind Farms, such as reducing their LCOE, specifically the OPEX and CAPEX, and increasing their reliability, there are technologies that foster the adoption of Offshore Wind Farms.

Enabling Technologies
Upscaling
Floating turbines
New materials
HVDC upscaling
Large-scale Storage
Advanced control
Advanced Maintenance Capabilities

3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

One of the main activities of the event was the co-creation session in order to interact with the audience. For that reason, a survey on the MENTIMETER online tool was prepared by APRE, adapted and translated by Q-PLAN and shared to the participants (in Greek) in order to collect useful information. It is common in such co-creation activities that some of the event participants didn't join the online tool.

The official results in Greek language along with the number of individual responses, as drawn from the MENTIMETER Tool, are presented in Annex I.

3.1 Question 1: Which of the following categories best represents you?

The attendees participated in the co-creation activities were mostly academics and stakeholders from civil society. In addition, there was adequate participation from business representatives, green innovation stakeholders, and public authorities. Finally, only two (2) participants chose the "other" option meaning that they categorize themselves in a different category. In total, 27 participants were actively engaged in the co-creation activities as indicated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Type of organisations involved

3.2 Question 2: What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on local economic activities (e.g., fishing, tourism)?

For this question, the participants were asked to select one option from the provided list about the impact they think Floating Offshore Wind Farms could have on local economic activities. Based on their responses, most of the participants believe that Floating Offshore Wind Farms will mostly have slightly negative to slightly positive impact, while a few participants believe that the impact on local economic activities will be either negative or positive.

Figure 11: Impact of FOWTs on local economic activities

It can be seen that there were opposite views from the audience regarding the impact of FOWTs on the local economic activities, showing that there are still a lot of controversies among the interested stakeholders.

3.3 Question 3: What kind of impact do you think floating offshore wind farms could have on the environment (e.g., biodiversity)?

For this question, the participants were asked to select one option from the provided list about the impact they think Floating Offshore Wind Farms could have on the environment. Based on their responses, most of the participants believe that Floating Offshore Wind Farms will have no impact at all on the environment. Moderately negative and Positive impact are the following most preferred options. In general, we see again that the opinions are divided regarding environmental impact of FOWTs.

Figure 12: Impact of FOWTs on the environment

3.4 Question 4: Do you think that floating offshore wind farms could bring benefits to the local community (e.g., economic benefits and energy savings, improvement of air quality, general improvement of quality of life)?

In the last question participants were asked to express if their opinion regarding the benefits that FOWTs could bring to the local communities. According to their responses, most of the participants strongly believe that FOWTs could bring benefits to the local communities, while almost all the participants are either neutral or agree that there are benefits for the local communities.

Figure 13: Opinion on the benefits of Floating Offshore Wind Farms on local communities

As a general remark, it's obvious that the participants were not opposite to the FOWTs in their region, but they are still afraid about potential negative impacts that could arise in various topics (environment, tourism, fishing). We believe that the lack of proper information from the public authorities about the FOWTs could greatly jeopardize the timely implementation of the National Programme for the Development of OWF in Greece.

4 ROUNDTABLE

The last session of the co-creation workshop included a roundtable among speakers and participants. The participants asked questions both on the speakers' presentations and on more general topics related to the installation of FOWTs in Crete. Due to the increased interest in the topic of FOWTs, the discussion had a strong flow, resulting in the exchange of various opinions and arguments regarding the perspective of FOWTs in Crete and Greece more broadly.

The discussion was mainly directed to the part of the benefits for the local community against the costs, mainly the in the tourism domain. The discussion showed that there is a positive response to such projects, but there are great doubts as to how much the local community can benefit from the FOWTs. Ideas emerged through the discussion, such as reducing electricity bills for local businesses and citizens, but also employing local citizens in the construction of the wind turbines. Responding to the idea of reducing electricity bills, Mr. Kyprakis outlined that FOWTs primarily contribute to the system stabilisation and reliability, and it is not a given that they will lead to reduced bills.

Apart from the benefits for local business and citizens, an important part of the discussion was the siting of the Floating Offshore Wind Farms. There have been significant reactions to the installation of offshore wind farms in the Greek territory and more specifically in the area of Crete. In particular, there have been reactions to the Elounda-Spinalonga areas from tourism associations and local stakeholders. In addition, several reactions occurred also regarding the selected area of Gyros due to the fact that is located in direct visual contact with the declared Historic Site of Gyros and is not consistent with its historical character. Most of the participants expressed their concerns on these matters, requesting from Minoan Energy Community to put pressure on the government, in terms of its decision to select these areas to install some of the first Floating Offshore Wind farms in Greece.

Finally, it was emphasized from participants that there should be full transparency and information towards local communities regarding the licensing and construction of such projects and that the government should establish public consultations necessary for the licensing and construction process to proceed. At the same time, local businesses, residents, and the energy community should participate in the construction of wind turbines in the form of ownership, in order to avoid possible profiteering by the owners.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The last of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Greek Lab has been mainly dedicated to social acceptance of FOWTs projects, but also to barriers and potential enablers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, as the previous co-creation workshops did. This time, specific focus was given to the civil society which shared their concerns regarding the offshore wind developments in Crete and Greece more broadly. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other. Several of them have been already detected during the previous co-creation workshops, thus validating our previous results.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Social acceptance of the Offshore Wind Farms There is a widespread resistance to the licensing and development of FOWTs in Greece due to civil society's and businesses' concerns regarding the potential benefits of such investments for the local community and economy.</p>	<p>Technological maturity The technological maturity of existing platforms, floating turbines, new materials along with the advanced maintenance technologies are considered enablers to invest in FOWTs.</p>
<p>Environmental impact The environmental impact of developing FOWT projects, particularly the impact on marine ecosystems, can result in significant delays and costs (e.g., further environmental impact studies), preventing potential investors to invest in FOWTs in Greece.</p>	<p>Greek offshore wind potential Greece has an extremely high offshore wind potential, thanks to the climate and the geographical position it holds on the energy map of Europe (e.g., stable winds, high intensity winds, etc.), thus attracting more investors.</p>
<p>Transparent licensing processes The lack of public consultations during the licensing process and continuous information to local communities may lead to resistance and delays during the construction phase of the project.</p>	<p>LCOE Even though, the LCOE of Offshore Wind Farms is higher than 0.10€/KWh, the downtrends are higher than expected, leading to more investments in FOWTs.</p>
<p>Lack of integrated Maritime Spatial Planning The lack of an integrated Maritime Spatial Planning in Greece is highlighted as a barrier on potential investments on offshore wind projects in Greece.</p>	<p>System stability and reliability FOWTs play significant role in the electrical system stability and reliability and it is considered as enabler for governments to invest in such technologies aiming to strengthen their national grid.</p>
<p>Reliability Due to weather and sea conditions, the reliability of FOWTs is dramatically reduced, if there is no proper maintenance, leading to loss-making investments.</p>	

6 ANNEX I – MENTIMETER TOOL RESULTS

Ποια απο τις παρακατω κατηγοριες σας αντιπροσωπευει καλυτερα;

Τι ειδους επιδραση πιστευετε πως θα εχουν τα Πλωτα Υπερακτια Αιολικα Παρκα στις τοπικες οικονομικες δραστηριοτητες (π.χ. τουρισμος, αλιεια);

Τι ειδους επιδραση πιστευετε πως θα εχουν τα Πλωτα Υπερακτια Αιολικα Παρκα στο περιβαλλον (π.χ., βιοποικιλοτητα);

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